

GASTROGRAFIN-ASSISTED RESOLUTION OF PEDIATRIC ADHESIVE SMALL BOWEL OBSTRUCTION: A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL CLINICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) is a common and serious complication in children after abdominal surgery, often requiring complex surgical intervention. Recently, interest has grown in using Gastrografin to help manage ASBO without surgery. This study was conducted to investigate its potential role as a treatment option in children not responding to initial conservative care.

Methods: This quasi-experimental study was conducted at The Children's Hospital, Lahore, between July 2023 and December 2024. Children with adhesive small bowel obstruction who didn't improve with initial conservative care were given a Gastrografin trial and monitored over 48 hours. Outcomes included clinical resolution, time to improvement, and need for surgery.

Results: Out of 32 children with adhesive small bowel obstruction, 26 (81.2%) responded successfully to the Gastrografin trial. Most showed improvement within 24 hours, avoiding the need for surgery. The average hospital stay after Gastrografin trial was 3 days, and no major complications related to contrast were reported.

Conclusion: Gastrografin was effective in resolving adhesive small bowel obstruction in most children, reducing the need for surgery and hospital stay. The findings suggest it can ease both medical and financial burdens. Larger trials and standardized protocols are needed to confirm and guide its future use.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesions form as part of the normal healing process after abdominal surgery and happen to be the leading cause of bowel obstruction.¹ Adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) is a major cause of postoperative morbidity in children. It presents diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive challenges, contributing to a significant socioeconomic burden.^{2,3} Intra-abdominal adhesions from previous surgery have been

reported to cause up to 75% of small bowel obstruction cases.⁴ ASBO appears to be more common in young children than in older ones, highlighting the need for separate studies to better understand its incidence and management.⁵ Recent data in some studies show the incidence of adhesive small bowel obstruction varying between 1% and 13% in children, depending on factors such as age and the

type of surgery. The risk is highest within the first year after surgery.² Literature reveals that the surgeries for adhesive small bowel obstruction are more complex, with higher morbidity, increased blood loss, and longer operative times. Studies also indicate that repeated surgery for ASBO raises the likelihood of readmission, bowel resection, and postoperative complications. The risk of bowel injury during surgery for small bowel obstruction has led to growing interest in conservative treatment approaches.⁶ The potential of adjunct therapies for managing ASBO without surgery is promising but remains uncertain. Several studies have explored the use of Gastrografin and other water-soluble contrast agents both as treatment options and as tools for identifying patients who may benefit from continued non-operative management.⁷ Findings from such studies suggest that using Gastrografin could help reduce the need for unnecessary surgical interventions.⁸ While its diagnostic role is well established, its therapeutic use is gaining interest.⁹ This study aims to explore the potential use of the commercially available contrast agent diatrizoate meglumine and diatrizoate sodium solution (Gastrografin) in managing ASBO in children after failed conservative treatment.

Methodology

This quasi-experimental study was conducted at The Children's Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan, from July 2023 to December 2024. Pediatric patients presenting to the emergency department with clinical and radiological evidence of adhesive small bowel obstruction (ASBO) and a history of prior abdominal surgery were included. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients exhibiting signs suggestive of strangulation or peritonitis at presentation, ongoing malignancy, and patients having a history of hypersensitivity to iodinated contrast.

A comprehensive initial assessment was conducted for all patients, including a detailed surgical and medical history, a thorough physical examination focusing on signs of bowel strangulation or peritonitis, and baseline investigations. Laboratory tests included a complete blood count, serum electrolytes, and renal function tests while radiological evaluation comprised plain abdominal radiographs in erect and supine positions. Patients with strangulation or peritonitis were explored after optimization in the emergency. The rest of the patients were managed conservatively for 24 hours according to institutional policy. The conservative treatment approach included bowel rest (NPO), nasogastric decompression, intravenous fluids for electrolyte imbalance, and rehydration. Those developing signs of strangulation or peritonitis during this period underwent surgical exploration. If no significant clinical or radiological improvement was observed after 24 hours, Gastrografin (a mixture of sodium amidotrizoate and meglumine amidotrizoate) trial was administered and monitored for 48 hours. To prevent dehydration caused by the hyperosmolar nature of Gastrografin, an intravenous Ringer's solution bolus was infused before its administration. Gastrografin was given according to the weight (3ml per kg) in equal dilution and administered through a nasogastric tube that was kept closed for 4 hours. Patients underwent serial abdominal X-rays at 3, 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours after Gastrografin administration. Treatment was considered successful if the contrast reached the cecum, accompanied by clinical improvement. Once this was achieved, the nasogastric tube was removed, and oral intake was gradually resumed, starting with clear fluids and progressing to solids. If the contrast failed to reach the large bowel within 48 hours, the obstruction was deemed complete, and the patient was scheduled for surgery.

Our institutional review board approved the study. A written informed consent was obtained from parents before inclusion. The collected data from the patients was analyzed with regard to the percentage of cases resolved after Gastrografin administration, time taken for resolution, and hospital stay in hours after Gastrografin administration. This study was conducted after receiving approval from the Institutional Review Board at the University of Child Health Sciences, Lahore. Informed written consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants. All procedures followed were in accordance with the ethical standards of the responsible committee and with the principles laid down in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

From the period of July 2023 and December 2024, a total of 32 patients presented with adhesive small bowel obstruction with no clinical or radiological

signs of strangulation or peritonitis. All patients were initially managed conservatively for the first 24 hours. This included keeping the patient nil per oral (NPO), placement of a nasogastric tube for gastrointestinal decompression, and administration of intravenous fluids to correct dehydration and electrolyte imbalances. In our study, the mean age was 5.7 years with the minimum age of the patient being 28 days and the maximum age being 15 years. 26 (81.2%) patients in our study were male and 6 (18.8%) were female. The initial or preceding surgical procedures in these patients were namely Stoma Reversal, Laparotomy for intussusception and Meckel’s diverticulum, and appendectomy among others as illustrated in Table 1. Three patients in our study did not have any previous records available with them regarding the preceding surgical procedures. All of them had a laparotomy scar and had undergone laparotomies at a private hospital.

Primary Condition	Number of Cases	Resolution of Obstruction	
		Yes	No
Intussusception	5	4	1
Reversal	7	7	0
Meckel Band	4	4	0

Appendectomy	4	2	2
Small Bowel Atresia	2	1	1
Necrotizing Enterocolitis	2	2	0
Band Obstruction	4	3	1
Open CDH Repair	1	1	0
No Previous Record available	3	2	1
Total	32	26	6

Table 1

All these patients were given a Gastrografin trial after an intravenous ringer lactate bolus and the response was observed. 26 (81.2%) patients were successfully managed, and the obstruction was resolved after the trial. Among these 26 patients, 25 patients' obstruction was resolved within 24 hours of the trial

while one patient's obstruction was resolved after 24 hours and within 48 hours. The 6 cases requiring surgery after the Gastrografin trial included postoperative cases of appendectomy and intussusception along with others.

Of the six patients who required surgery following a failed Gastrografin trial, two were found to have a volvulus caused by a constricting band, while another had a band obstruction severe enough to cause complete blockage, though without volvulus. Two patients underwent adhesiolysis, with one requiring the formation of an ileostomy due to extensive adhesions. Additionally, one patient with a history of

appendectomy required both adhesiolysis and burial of the appendiceal stump.

Since almost all of the patient's obstruction was resolved in 24 hours, the average hospital stay in this study was 3 days from the day of the Gastrografin trial bringing the total stay on an average to 4 days. Also, no significant complications were observed following the administration of the Gastrografin in this study.

Figure 3 showing contrast in small intestine

Figure 4 showing contrast crossed ICJ

Figure showing contrast in descending colon

Discussion

Gastrografin administration offers a valuable non-operative strategy in the management of pediatric small bowel obstruction, particularly in cases attributed to postoperative adhesions.¹⁰ A 2013 systematic review assessed the outcomes of non-surgical management strategies for adhesive small bowel obstruction in the pediatric population, with a few cases incorporating Gastrografin. The findings of this systematic review emphasized the wide variation in success rates across studies and underscored the

need for standardized treatment protocols to guide clinical decision-making.¹¹ Small bowel obstruction poses a major clinical concern due to its impact on patients' fluid and electrolyte balance, as well as the mechanical consequences of increased intraluminal pressure, which can compromise bowel wall perfusion and lead to ischemia.¹²

A key limitation in current research on the use of water-soluble contrast agents in adhesive small intestinal obstruction is the lack of standardized study designs. Variations in protocols, contrast agent

characteristics, and administered volumes make it challenging to draw consistent and generalizable conclusions.¹³ Gastrografin is a high-osmolar, water-soluble contrast agent and it derives its therapeutic benefit largely due to its hyperosmolar properties, which draw fluid into the intestinal lumen, reduce bowel wall edema, and enhance peristalsis.^{14,15,16} Gastrografin has an osmolarity of about 1900 mOsm/L, making it roughly six times more concentrated than normal extracellular fluid.¹⁷

The most common initial presentation and procedure that subsequently led to adhesive obstruction was stoma reversal followed by intussusception, Meckel's diverticulum, and appendicitis as illustrated in Table 1. A study conducted in Taiwan identified appendicitis and Hirschsprung disease as the most common underlying causes of adhesive small bowel obstruction. Notably, they observed 10 episodes of ASBO in just three patients with Hirschsprung disease.⁴ In contrast, our study did not include any cases of Hirschsprung disease, which may suggest that patients with this condition who presented during the study period likely had more severe symptoms, making them unsuitable for conservative treatment approaches. A systematic review of pediatric ASBO corroborated that open surgeries in general increase the risk of ASBO in comparison to laparoscopy. The review also noted that in neonates, common underlying causes include gastroschisis, necrotizing enterocolitis, meconium ileus, and malrotation, whereas, in older children, previous open abdominal surgeries in general and appendectomies were the most frequently reported contributors.¹⁸

We report a success rate of 81.2% (n=26) in the successful resolution of ASBO by Gastrografin administration. A study from Cairo, Egypt reported a 66.7% success rate in treating adhesive small bowel obstruction using Gastrografin.¹⁹ Another Egyptian study observed a slightly higher success rate of 70%, reinforcing the potential role of Gastrografin as an effective non-operative option in selected pediatric cases.²⁰ Additional studies in the literature also support the potential advantages of using Gastrografin in managing ASBO. However, many of these studies were limited by small sample sizes and

further subgroup divisions, making it challenging to draw broad, definitive conclusions.

A study conducted in France comparing the conservative management of ABSO in the pediatric population to conservative management with Gastrografin identified that the length of hospital stay was halved on an average.⁶ Most studies to date have primarily focused on the time taken for obstruction to resolve following Gastrografin administration, rather than assessing metrics like the average length of hospital stay. This aligns with our findings, where resolution typically occurred within 24 hours of administration.

An interesting pattern observed in the literature is the variation in how Gastrografin is diluted prior to administration. Similar to our protocol, several centers opted to mix it in a 1:1 ratio with Ringer's lactate.^{19,21} In contrast, one Taiwanese study used twice the volume for dilution, while a French study only reported the volume without any mention of the dilution.^{6,8} Another point of divergence lies in how the dosage was determined: many studies used fixed-volume dosing according to patient age brackets, highlighting the absence of a universally accepted dosing standard. In contrast, we calculated the volume of Gastrografin based on the patient's weight. This weight-based approach allows for more precise dosing tailored to individual patient physiology, reducing the risk of under or overdosing, especially in younger children where weight can vary significantly within the same age group.

Conclusion

This study supports the use of Gastrografin in managing adhesive small bowel obstruction in children, with 81.2% of cases successfully treated. This helped minimize morbidity and also reduced the overall financial strain on families and healthcare systems. Despite a small sample size, the results suggest a promising role for Gastrografin in avoiding operative intervention in ABSO. However, we recognize that there is a clear need for large-scale randomized controlled trials to further evaluate its effectiveness, particularly regarding recurrence rates and long-term outcomes. In addition, the lack of standardized protocols for administration further

highlights the importance of establishing clear guidelines to optimize its use.

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